

and without inhibitor are shown in Fig. 2. It will be seen that in the absence of any inhibitor there is both cathodic and anodic polarisation but the anodic polarisation is considerably increased in presence of inhibitor. The polarisation measurements indicate that chromate controls the anodic process. High polarisation of the anodes at low current densities indicate film formation at the

Fig. 2. Polarisation of mild steel in (O) uninhibited and (x) inhibited 10^{-1} M NaCl solution.

anode sites. The protective effect of chromate is due to the formation of passive film^{16,17}. Rajagopalan *et al.*¹⁸ also proved the formation of a passive film by chromate by electron diffraction, radio-tracer and cathodic reduction techniques. The Tafel parameters and inhibitor efficiency were calculated¹⁹ and are given in Table 4. The inhibition efficiency calculated from Tafel parameters (99.99%) is in close

TABLE 4—TAFEL PARAMETERS AND INHIBITION EFFICIENCY

Solution	Tafel slope (anodic)	Corrosion current of anodic Tafel line mA cm^{-2}	Inhibitor efficiency (%)	
			From anodic Tafel line	From wt. loss method
10^{-1} M NaCl	0.30	1×10^{-1}	—	—
10^{-1} M NaCl + 3% chromate	0.16	1×10^{-5}	99.99	100.00

agreement with the value (100%) calculated from weight loss measurements.

Conclusion: The corrosion of mild steel is reduced and the potential ennobled as the concentration of chromate is increased in aqueous solution of chloride. Chromate remained effective at high temperature (upto 80°) and for long test durations. The mechanism of the action of the inhibitor in aqueous solution of chloride indicates that it is an anodic inhibitor.

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Effect of Natural Products isolated from Three Species of *Sida* on some Gram-positive and Gram-negative Bacteria

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BALAS, the different species of *Sida*, (fam: *Malvaceae*) are well known as valuable drugs in Ayurvedic and Unani systems of medicine. Considering their medicinal uses¹⁻³, three species of this genus, i.e. *Sida acuta* Burm., *S. veronicaefolia* Lam. and *S. rhombifolia* Linn. have been selected in order to find out the active constituents of these plants against some gram-positive and some gram-negative bacteria.

Experimental

The air-dried and finely powdered plant materials of *S. acuta* Burm., *S. veronicaefolia* Lam. and *S. rhombifolia* Linn. (collected from the surroundings of Aligarh district) were separately extracted with light petroleum (b.p. 60–80°). The extracts after removal of the solvent under reduced pressure were steam-distilled and saponified by refluxing with a solution of 0.5 N KOH for 6 h. The unsaponifiable fractions of the three plants, separately on chromatographic separation over the column of silica gel, gave three fractions each: (i) alkanes, (ii) alkanols and (iii) sterols. The glc analysis of alkanes, alkanols and acetyl derivative of sterol fractions showed the different composition in each of the three species of *Sida* (Table 1).

Fractions	<i>S. acuta</i>	<i>S. veronicaefolia</i>	<i>S. rhombifolia</i>
Alkanes	C ₁₇ –C ₂₃	C ₁₅ –C ₂₅	C ₁₅ –C ₂₅
Alkanols	C ₁₇ –C ₂₃	C ₁₇ –C ₂₅	C ₁₄ –C ₂₃
Sterols	Cholesterol	Cholesterol	Cholesterol
	Campesterol	22-Dehydrocampesterol	22-Dehydrocampesterol
	Stigmasterol	Campesterol	Campesterol
	β-Sitosterol	Stigmasterol	24-Methylene cholesterol
	Stigmast-7-enol	β-Sitosterol	Stigmasterol
		Δ ⁸⁽¹⁴⁾ -Stigmasterol	Sitosterol Δ ⁸⁽¹⁴⁾ -Stigmasterol Spinasterol 22-Dihydro-spinasterol

TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS AGAINST GRAM-POSITIVE BACTERIA*

Compd	<i>S. aureus</i>		<i>S. albus</i>		<i>B. subtilis</i>	
	1 mg ml ⁻¹	0.5 mg ml ⁻¹	1 mg ml ⁻¹	0.5 mg ml ⁻¹	1 mg ml ⁻¹	0.5 mg ml ⁻¹
Alkanes (<i>S. acuta</i>)	++	++	++	+	++	+
Alkanes (<i>S. veronicaefolia</i>)	++	++	++	+	++	+
Alkanes (<i>S. rhombifolia</i>)	++	++	++	+	++	+
Alkanols (<i>S. acuta</i>)	—	—	—	—	—	—
Alkanols (<i>S. veronicaefolia</i>)	—	—	—	—	—	—
Alkanols (<i>S. rhombifolia</i>)	—	—	—	—	—	—
Sterol (<i>S. acuta</i>)	+++	+	++	+	—	—
Sterol (<i>S. veronicaefolia</i>)	+++	+	++	+	—	—
Sterol (<i>S. rhombifolia</i>)	+++	++	+++	++	+	—
Steryl acetate (<i>S. acuta</i>)	++	+	+	+	—	—
Steryl acetate (<i>S. veronicaefolia</i>)	++	+	+	+	—	—
Steryl acetate (<i>S. rhombifolia</i>)	++	+	++	+	—	—
Sitosteryl acetate (<i>S. acuta</i>)	++	+	+	+	—	—
Sitosteryl acetate (<i>S. veronicaefolia</i>)	++	+	+	+	—	—
Sitosteryl acetate (<i>S. rhombifolia</i>)	++	+	+	+	—	—
Stigmasteryl acetate (<i>S. acuta</i>)	++	+	+	+	—	—
Stigmasteryl acetate (<i>S. veronicaefolia</i>)	++	+	+	+	—	—
Stigmasteryl acetate (<i>S. rhombifolia</i>)	++	+	+	+	—	—

* Increase in diameter of zone of inhibition: (+)=0.2 cm, (++)=0.4 cm, (+++)=0.6 cm, and (—)=inactive.

TABLE 3—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS AGAINST GRAM-NEGATIVE BACTERIA*

Compd.	<i>E. coli</i>		<i>Klebsiella</i>		<i>S. dysenterias</i>		<i>P. vulgaris</i>		<i>P. pyocyanea</i>	
	1 mg ml ⁻¹	0.5 mg ml ⁻¹	1 mg ml ⁻¹	0.5 mg ml ⁻¹	1 mg ml ⁻¹	0.5 mg ml ⁻¹	1 mg ml ⁻¹	0.5 mg ml ⁻¹	1 mg ml ⁻¹	0.5 mg ml ⁻¹
Alkanes (<i>S. acuta</i>)	+++	++	++	+	+++	++	++	+	+++	+
Alkanes (<i>S. veronicaefolia</i>)	+++	++	++	+	+++	++	++	+	+++	+
Alkanes (<i>S. rhombifolia</i>)	+++	++	++	+	+++	++	++	+	+++	+
Alkanols (<i>S. acuta</i>)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Alkanols (<i>S. veronicaefolia</i>)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Alkanols (<i>S. rhombifolia</i>)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Sterol (<i>S. acuta</i>)	+++	++	++	+	+	—	++	+	++	+
Sterol (<i>S. veronicaefolia</i>)	+++	++	++	+	+	—	++	+	++	+
Sterol (<i>S. rhombifolia</i>)	+++	++	++	+	+	—	++	+	++	+
Steryl acetate (<i>S. acuta</i>)	++	+	+	—	—	—	+	+	+	—
Steryl acetate (<i>S. veronicaefolia</i>)	++	+	+	—	—	—	+	+	+	—
Steryl acetate (<i>S. rhombifolia</i>)	++	+	++	+	+	—	++	+	+	+
Sitosteryl acetate (<i>S. acuta</i>)	++	+	—	—	+	—	+	+	+	+
Sitosteryl acetate (<i>S. veronicaefolia</i>)	++	+	—	—	+	—	+	+	+	+
Sitosteryl acetate (<i>S. rhombifolia</i>)	++	+	—	—	+	—	+	+	+	+
Stigmasteryl acetate (<i>S. acuta</i>)	++	+	+	—	+	—	+	+	+	+
Stigmasteryl acetate (<i>S. veronicaefolia</i>)	++	+	+	—	+	—	+	+	+	+
Stigmasteryl acetate (<i>S. rhombifolia</i>)	++	+	+	—	+	—	+	+	+	+

* Explanations as in Table 2.

Two major products (stigmasteryl acetate and sitosteryl acetate) were separated from the above mixture of steryl acetate by argentation (silica gel - 20% AgNO₃) column chromatography. These alongwith other isolated components from the three species of *Sida* were, separately, screened *in vitro* against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus albus* and *Bacillus subtilis* (gram-positive), and *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella*, *Shigella dysenteriae*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Pseudomonas pyocyanea* (gram-negative).

Results and Discussion

The antibacterial activity shown by different compounds isolated from the *Sida* species indicates that the longchain hydrocarbons are active against both the gram-positive and the gram-negative bacteria while alcohols are totally inactive and that sterols are active against selected bacteria except *B. subtilis*. The introduction of acetyl group in sterol decreases the activity of the compounds. (Tables 2 and 3). When these compounds were tested at half concentration, their activity showed relative decrease in most cases but remained similar in few cases. Thus it may be concluded that hydrocarbons and sterols are active constituents of these plants against the selected microorganisms.

The interesting observation reported earlier that β -sitosterol possess anti-inflammatory activity, similar to hydrocortisone and oxyphenbutazone, and antipyretic activity similar to acetyl salicylic acid⁶, also suggests that the presence of β -sitosterol in these plants might be responsible for their medicinal value.

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